

Effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among intubated patients admitted in ICU at selected hospitals

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Abstract:-

Background: Care bundles are a collection of three to five practices that are supported by evidence and are consistently applied to raise the standard of care. In order to prevent and treat various health disorders, care bundles are frequently employed in healthcare settings. This is the first systematic review done to ascertain how care bundles affect patient outcomes and how healthcare professionals behave in terms of loyalty to care bundles **Material and Method:** Quantitative evaluative research approach with quasi experimental post test only design was adopted for the study. Through Non-Probability Convenient Sampling Technique, 40 patients on intubation were selected, among them 20 patients selected as experimental group and 20 patients were selected as control group. Their post-test level of ventilator-associated pneumonia was evaluated using the Clinical Pulmonary Infection Score (CPIS), and demographic data were gathered using a semi- structured interviewing schedule. **Result:** During the post test, patients in experimental group 5(25%) did not develop infection. However, 11(55%) patients developed mild infection and 4(20%) patients developed severe infection. Among control group 7(35%) patients developed mild infection and 13(65%) patients developed severe infection. However, the post-test mean score for the experimental group was 1.7 ± 1.04 and for the control group it was 2.95 ± 1.76 . The mean difference was found 31. The calculated value was found to be 5.20.this is found greater than the table value of 2.02, significant at $p \leq 0.05$ levels. Hence the research hypothesis H1 was accepted. There was no association between the selected demographic characteristics and the prevention of ventilator-associated pneumonia in the experimental or control group. This demonstrates that the care bundle was successful in reducing ventilator- associated pneumonia in incubated patients. **Conclusion:** When compared to standard treatment, the use of care bundles may be an effective way to enhance patient outcomes, according to very low quality evidence from controlled before-after trials. In contrast, the low-quality evidence from five randomized trial is highly uncertain.

KEYWORDS: care bundle, ventilator, pneumonia, and intubation.

Introduction:-

Human body needs constant supply of oxygen to support the body's metabolism. Respiration is one of the processes needed for survival and also provides the necessary energy or carrying on all essential life processes. It is the process by which an organism exchanges gases with its environment. The respiratory tract is the track of air from the nose to the lungs. Upper Respiratory Tract and Lower Respiratory Tract are the two portions that make up this organ. The nasal cavities, larynx, pharynx, epiglottis, and nostrils are all parts of the upper respiratory system. Lungs, Trachea, Bronchi, and Bronchioles make up the lower respiratory system. The respiratory system's organs ensure that oxygen enters our bodies and carbon dioxide exits. The respiratory system plays a vital role in the inhalation and exhalation of respiratory gases in the human body.¹ A mechanical ventilator is a breathing device that can maintain ventilation and oxygen delivery for a prolonged per period of time. Intubation has become the most commonly used mode of life-support in medicine today. Intubation is often a life saving, but like other interventions, it is not without complications. Physiologic complications associated with mechanical ventilation include ventilator induced lung injury, cardiovascular compromise, gastrointestinal disturbances, pneumothorax and the most importantly ventilator associated pneumonia. The second-most prevalent nosocomial illness worldwide is pneumonia and is a leading cause of death due to hospital acquired infections. In addition to their severe disease, patients in the intensive care unit (ICU) also run the risk of dying from ancillary conditions including nosocomial infections. 27% of all critically sick patients have hospital acquired pneumonia, the second most frequent nosocomial infection in this population. Ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) is a form of nosocomial pneumonia that occurs in patients receiving intubation of within 48 hours.²

Risk factors for VAP are multiple and are divided into those that are modifiable and those that are non-modifiable. Modifiable factors include the supine position, gastric over distension, improper suctioning, pooling of the secretion, contamination of ventilator circuits, frequent patient transfers, instillation of normal saline, understaffing, non-conformance to hand washing protocol, indiscriminate use of antibiotics, and lack of training in VAP prevention and low pressure of the endotracheal tube (ETT) cuff. Non modifiable factors include male gender, age over 60 years, acute respiratory distress syndrome, multiple organ failure, coma, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, tracheostomy, re-intubation, neurosurgery and cranial trauma. The onset of VAP can be divided into 2 types: early onset and late onset. Early onset VAP occurs within 48 hours to 96 hours after intubation and is associated with antibiotic susceptible organisms. Late onset VAP occurs more than 96 hours after intubation and is associated with antibiotic resistant bacteria.³

NEED FOR STUDY: Intensive care units have come to represent the most frequently identifiable source of nosocomial infection within hospital, with the infection rates and rate of antimicrobial resistance several fold greater than General hospital settings. VAP is considered the most common nosocomial infection in the intensive care unit (ICU) and is also a major threat to the recovery of patients receiving intubation. According to The National Nosocomial Infection Surveillance Program the incidence of VAP is 7.6 cases per 1000 patient ventilator days. The number of VAP cases per 1000 ventilator days, is the standard measure for surveillance by the CDC and are outlined in CDC guidelines. The incidence of VAP ranges from 28-32% in patients receiving intubation. A patient's hospital stay is extended by an

additional 7-9 days on average when VAP is present. Early on in the hospital stay, the risk of VAP is highest; it is predicted to be 3%/day for the first 5 days of ventilation, 2%/day for days 5 through 10, and 1%/day for days 11 through 20.⁴ VAP is always associated with increase in morbidity and mortality, hospital length of stay and costs. VAP may develop any time during ventilation, but occurs more often in the first few days after intubation. This is because the intubation process itself contributes to the development of VAP. Although VAP has multiple risk factors, many nursing interventions can reduce the incidence of occurrence of VAP. The concept of care bundle is based on the fact that delivering evidence-based interventions reliably and consistently will improve patient care. A bundle is a collection of several evidence-based practices which should be implemented together on a daily basis. The use of 'bundles' has grown in popularity throughout health care due to the quality improvement movement.⁵ Care bundle prevent the occurrence of VAP through the implementation of simple, low cost preventive measures. The VAP prevention bundle is now become a central component of most critical care patient safety programme. The key components included in care bundle are proper hand washing, head of bed elevation to 30° to 40°, peptic ulcer disease (PUD) prophylaxis, deep vein thrombosis (DVT) prophylaxis, daily ventilator weaning assessment, daily sedationvacation, Maintaining the ET tube cuff pressure, oral care with chlorhexidine mouth wash, closed system suctioning & turning the patient at least every 3 hours. Interventions to prevent VAP begin at the time of intubation and should be continued until extubation.⁶

STATEMENT

A study to evaluate the effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among intubated patients admitted in ICU at selected hospitals.

OBJECTIVES:

Primary Objectives:

1. To assess the effect of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients admitted in ICU experimental group.
2. To assess the effect of hospital existing protocol on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients admitted in ICU in control group.
3. To compare the effect of hospital existing protocol and care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among incubated patients.
4. To find out association between the effect of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among intubated patents and there socio demographic variable.

Secondary Objectives:

1. To assess the ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation in experimental and control group.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on ventilator in experimental group and control group.

3. To associate the post test score on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on ventilator with their selected demographic variables in experimental and control group.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION:

- **Effectiveness:** Effectiveness is defined as a degree to which responses to message transmission event is consonant with overall objectives of the sender of the event.²⁰
- **Care Bundle:** A “care bundle is a collection of interventions that may be applied to the management of a particular condition.”⁷
- **Ventilator Associated Pneumonia:** A nosocomial pneumonia that develops at least 48 hours after initiation of intubation.⁸
- **Endotracheal Intubation:** Endotracheal intubation is the medical procedure in which a tube is placed into the trachea (Wind Pipe) through the mouth or nose. Most often, it is inserted through the mouth in emergency situations.⁹

HYPOTHESIS:

- **H0:** There will be no significant difference in post test score on prevention of VAP among patients on intubation in experimental and control group.
- **H01:** There will be significant difference in post test score on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation in experimental and control group at $p \leq 0.05$ level.
- **H02:** There will be significant association between post test score on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation with their selected demographic variables in experimental group and control group at $p \leq 0.05$ level.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Ventilator associated pneumonia.**
2. **Effectiveness of Ventilator bundle on prevention of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia.**
 - **Ventilator associated pneumonia.**

(M. V. Pravin Charles, et, al, 2013) A prospective study was conducted at a tertiary care teaching hospital in Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute, Pondicherry for finding out the incidence and risk factors associated with VAP. Patients who were on intubation were closely monitored frequently for development of VAP with the help of clinical pulmonary infection score. The results showed that out of the 76 patients, 18 (23.7%) developed VAP during their ICU stay. The incidence of VAP was 53.25 per 1,000 ventilator days. About 94% of VAP cases occurred within the first week of MV. Early-onset and late-onset VAP was observed in 72.2% and 27.8% cases respectively. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (33.3%) was the most common organism isolated from VAP patients. It was followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (20.8%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (8.3%), *Candida albicans* (8.3%), *Escherichia coli* (8.3%), and *Acinetobacter baumannii* (4.2%).¹⁰

(Yogesh Harde, et.al, 2013)A prospective study was done by Jawaharlal institute of post graduate medical education and research (JIPMER) hospital in Pondicherry, to determine the incidence and the risk factors for development of VAP among mechanically ventilated patients. In this study the incidence of VAP was 30.67 and 15.87 in the two different ICUs and 58.3 % of the cases were early- onset VAP, while 41.7 % were late- onset VAP. The study identifies the risk factors for VAP include impaired consciousness, improper suctioning, tracheostomy, re-intubation, emergency intubation, and nasogastric tube feeding. *Acinetobacter Baumannii* was the most prevalent organism, followed by *Enterobacteraceae*. *Enterobacteraceae* and *Acinetobacter*, which cause late VAP, caused early VAP. The study found that, when used sensibly, the CPIS score can be a pretty accurate way to detect VAP in critically ill patients while also helping to limit the overuse of antibiotics¹¹

(Vishal B Shete, et. al, 2011)A retrospective study was done in BJ medical college and hospital pune, Maharashtra, to find out the incidence of *Acinetobacter* infection in VAP cases, and to determine the antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of *Acinetobacter*. An incidence of 11.6% of *Acinetobacter* VAP cases was recorded. *Acinetobacter* VAP has been linked to a number of underlying diseases, including head trauma, cerebral hemorrhage, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). The study concluded that Ventilator- Associated Pneumonia (VAP) is mainly due to the multi-drug resistant (MDR) bacterias mainly, *Acinetobacter* species which is one of the most dreadful complications, occurring in the critical care setting.¹²

Review related to Effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia:

(Rello J, et. al, 2013)A collaborative multi-centre cohort study was conducted in five Spanish adult intensive-care units. The aim of the study was the implementation of care bundles for prevention of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) and its impact on patient outcomes requires validation with long- term follow- up. Five measures made up a care bundle approach that was put into practice. The baseline period involved 149 patients, and the intervention phase involved 85 patients. Following the intervention, the incidence of VAP dropped from 15.5% (23/149) to 11.7% (104/885) (p 0.05). This reduction was significantly associated with hand hygiene, intra –cuff pressure control, oral hygiene and head elevation. Patients with full bundle compliance (intervention period) had shorter median ICU stays (from 10 to 6 days) and shorter durations of mechanical breathing (from 8 to 4 days). The study concluded that the care bundle was effective in preventing VAP among intubated patients.¹³

(Bukhari. S.Z, et.al, 2012)A prospective longitudinal study was conducted on adult intensive care unit (ICU) at Hera general hospital, makkah, kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study's objectives were to lower the incidence rate of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP), lower healthcare costs, and link care bundle compliance to VAP incidence rate. VAP prevention bundle applied was: head- of –bed elevation; daily sedation-vacation along with a readiness- to-wean assessment; closed system suctioning; and deep venous thrombosis (DVT) prophylaxis. The results showed that the VAP incidence decreases from 26.3% to 10.2%. A significant correlation was found between the VAP rate and its bundle compliance (p≤0.05). Most frequent pathogens found were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (30.8% of all isolates) followed by *Acinetobacter baumannii* (27.7%), and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (15.4%). The study concludes that the application of VAP prevention bundle reduced the VAP incidence rate and lowered the cost of care.¹⁴

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach: The research approach used for this study was quantitative evaluative approach.

Research Design: The research design chosen for this study was quasi experimental post test only design. The design can be represented as,

Population: The population of the study comprises of patients on intubation at selected hospitals.

Sampling Sample: The sample of this study comprises of patients on intubation admitted in ICU at selected hospitals during the study period and those who met the inclusion criteria.

Sample Size: Sample size of the study was 40 patients on intubation. Among them 20 patients were selected to the experimental group and 20 patients were selected to the control group.

Sampling Technique: The investigator selected the samples by non probability convenient sampling technique

Independent Variable: The independent variable of the study was care bundle.

Dependent Variable: The dependent variable was ventilator associated pneumonia.

Criteria for Sample Selection:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients with age group between 20–60years.
- Patients who receive intubation.
- Both male and female patients.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients after 24 hours of intubation.
- Patients already diagnosed with fever, pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome.
- Patients with cervical and spinal cord injury.
- Patients already incubated from outside hospital

Section A: Demographic Variables:

This section consists of demographic variables like age, sex, reason for, frequency of suctioning, frequency of changing the position & history of smoking. The baseline data were collected by using semi structured interview schedule.

Section B: Modified Clinical Pulmonary Infection Score (CPIS) for Assessing Ventilator Associated Pneumonia:

The Clinical Pulmonary Infection Score has utility in both detecting the onset of ventilator associated pneumonia and also determining the sufficiency and adequacy of treatment. The diagnosis of ventilator associated pneumonia was generally based upon variations of the Clinical Pulmonary Infection Score originally developed by Pugnet al., in 1990.

Validity: The tool was validated by obtaining opinion from 2 medical experts and 4 nursing experts. Experts were requested to judge the tool for its content clarity, sequence and meaningfulness. Appropriate modifications were made according to the opinion of medical and nursing experts and tool was finalized.

Reliability:

The reliability of the tool was checked and established by using inter rater method $r = 1$ which showed that the tool was reliable and considered for proceeding.

Pilot Study: It was conducted with the sample size of 20 patients on intubation, from experimental group and 20 patients on intubation selected for control group. Care bundle was provided for 3 days to the experimental group. Routine care with endotracheal suctioning was done to the control group. Post test assessment was done on the 4th day for both experimental group and control group by using modified Clinical Pulmonary Infection Score (CPIS).

Ethical consideration: Written permission was obtained from the managing director of selected hospitals.

Plan for Data Analysis:

The data were analyzed by using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The data related to demographic variables were analyzed by using descriptive measures (frequency & percentage) and the ventilator associated pneumonia was analyzed by using descriptive statistics (mean & standard deviation). The effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia were analyzed by Unpaired 't' test. The association between ventilator associated pneumonia and demographic variables were analyzed by using inferential statistics (chi-square test).

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION**SECTION- A:**

- Distribution of patients according to their Demographic variables.

Table No-I**n = 40**

S. No	Demographic Variables	Experimental Group n = 20		Control Group n = 20	
		f	%	f	%
1. Age in years	a) 20 –30	6	30	2	10
	b) 31 –40	5	25	4	20
	c) 41 –50	4	20	7	35
	d) 51 –60	5	25	7	35
	2. Gender				
a) Male	14	70	15	75	
b) Female	6	30	5	25	
3. Reason for intubation	a) CNS Disease	9	45	7	35
	b) Cardiac Disease	3	15	3	15
	c) Renal Disease	2	10	3	15
	d) Poisoning	5	25	3	15
	e) Others	1	5	4	20
	4. Frequency of suctioning				
a) 2 nd hourly	12	60	6	30	
b) 3 rd hourly	8	40	8	40	
c) 4 th hourly	-	-	6	30	
5. History of smoking	a) Yes	10	50	11	55
	b) No	10	50	9	45

SECTION- B:

- a. **Distribution of patients according to the post test score on prevention of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia in Experimental group.** A experimental group 5(25%) patients on intubation have no infection, 11(55%) patients on intubation have mild infection and 4(20%) patients on incubator have severe infection
- b. **Distribution of patients according to post test score on prevention of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia in Control group.**

in control group 7(35%) patients on intubation have mild infection and 13(65%) patients on intubation have severe infection.

SECTION- C:

- a. **Comparison of post test score on prevention of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia among patients on intubation in experimental and control group.**

That 5(25%) of the patients on intubation have no infection in experimental group. In experimental group 11 (55%) of the patients and in control group 7(35%) of the patients on intubation have mild infection. In experimental group 4(20%) of the patients and in control group 13(65%) of the patients on intubation have severe infection. It reveals that most of the patients in experimental group have mild infection and most of the patients in control group have severe infection.

- b. **Mean, Standard Deviation and Mean difference on prevention of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia among patients on intubation in experimental & control group**

Table No-II
40

n =

Groups	aximum Score	Post test			Difference in Mean%
		Mean	SD	Mean%	
Experimental group	5	1.7	1.04	28	31
Control group	5	2.95	1.76	59	

SECTION- D:

- a. **Effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia among patients on intubation in experimental group.**

Table No-III

n= 40

Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	't' value	Table Value
Experimental group	1.7	1.04	38	5.20*	2.02
Control group	2.95	1.76			

*significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level

b. Association between prevention of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia among patients on intubation in experimental & control group with their selected Demographic variables.

Table No-IV

n =

40

S. No	Demographic variables	Experimental group n = 20			Control group n = 20		
		Df	χ^2	Table value	df	χ^2	Table value
1.	Age in years	6	2.76	12.59	3	6.26	7.82
2.	Gender	2	1.9	5.99	1	.65	3.84
3	Reason for intubation	8	4.07	15.51	4	3.46	9.49
4	Frequency of suctioning	2	4.06	5.99	2	4.43	5.99
5	History of smoking	2	1.2	5.99	1	.09	3.84

*Significant at $p \geq 0.05$ level

DISCUSSION

Frequency and percentage distribution of patients according to their demographic variables in experimental and control group.

The distribution of patients according to their demographic variables showed that in experimental group 6(30%) patients were between the age group of 20 – 30years and in control group 7(35%) patients were between the age group of 51 – 60years. Majority of the patients in experimental 14(70%) group and in control 15(75%) group were male. In experimental and control group 9(45%) and 7(35%) patients were ventilated due to CNS Disease problems respectively. In experimental group 12 (60%) the majority of patients underwent second hourly suctioning, while in control group 8 (40%) the majority of patients underwent third hourly suctioning. Patients in control group 11 (55%) and experimental group 10 (50%) both had a history of smoking.

Assessment of ventilator associated pneumonia in experimental and control group.

In experimental group 5(25%) patients had no infection, 11(55%) patients had mild infection and 4(20%) patients have severe infection. In control group 7(35%) patients had mild infection and 13(65%) patients had severe infection.

Effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation.

In experimental group the post test mean score was 1.7 ± 1.04 and the mean percentage was 28. In control group the post test mean score was 2.95 ± 1.76 and mean percentage was 59. The difference in mean percentage was 31. The 't' value was 5.20 which was greater than the table value 2.02, significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level.

Association of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation with their selected demographic variables.

The present study finding revealed that, there was no association in experimental and control group on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia with the selected demographic variables such as age, sex, reason for intubation, frequency of suctioning and history of smoking. Hence H_2 was rejected among patients on intubation with their selected demographic variables at $p \geq 0.05$ level.

SUMMARY:

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation. A quasi experimental post test only study design was conducted in Selected hospitals, 40 patients were selected, according to the patients receiving intubation. Out of 40 patients on intubation, 20 patients on intubation were selected to experimental group and 20 patients on intubation were selected to control group by using Non probability convenient sampling technique. Immediately after Endotracheal Intubation, care bundle was provided for 3 days to the experimental group. The care bundle includes head elevation of 30 degree, closed system suctioning and changing the position of patient every 3 hourly. Post test assessment was done on the 4th day of experimental group and control group by using modified Clinical Pulmonary Infection Score (CPIS).

The baseline data was tabulated by formulating frequency table. The ventilator associated pneumonia was analyzed by using descriptive statistics. The effectiveness of care bundle was evaluated by unpaired 't' test. The chi-square analysis was done to associate the ventilator associated pneumonia with their selected demographic variables.

CONCLUSION:

The study was done to evaluate the effectiveness of care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation at selected hospitals. The result of this study showed that care bundle was effective in preventing the ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation in experimental group. There was no association found between the prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia with the selected demographic variables in experimental and control group. Hence research hypothesizes₂ was rejected at $p \geq 0.05$ level.

IMPLICATION:

The findings of the study have the following implications in the various areas of nursing service, nursing education, nursing administration and nursing research.

NURSING SERVICES:

- The present study can be utilized by nurses to understand the importance of care bundle for the prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on intubation.

NURSING EDUCATION:

- The nurse educator can use the concept about the care bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia to teach in educational settings.

NURSING ADMINISTRATION:

- Nurse administrator can arrange training programs on care bundle and closed system suctioning of end tracheal tube for the prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia.

NURSING RESEARCH:

- The findings of the present study can be used by other researchers to conduct further researches.

RECOMMENDATION:

- A similar study can be conducted with large group.
- A similar study can be conducted in various settings to identify the factors influencing ventilator associated pneumonia.

REFERENCE

1. B. D. Chaurasia, Benumof's Airway Management (3rd edition) Miller's...B. D. Chaurasia Human Anatomy Grays Anatomy E-books.70.
2. Al-Moamary MS. Annals of Thoracic Medicine ... a three-year journey. Ann Thorac Med. 2009 Jan;4(1):1-2. doi: 10.4103/1817-1737.44776. PMID: 19561912; PMCID:PMC2700476.
3. Robert A. Weinstein, Marc J. M. Bonten, Marin H. Kollef, Jesse B. Hall, Risk Factors for Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia: From Epidemiology to Patient Management, Clinical Infectious Diseases, Volume 38, Issue 8, 15 April 2004, Pages 1141–1149, <https://doi.org/10.1086/383039>.
4. Augustyn B. Ventilator-associated pneumonia: risk factors and prevention. Critical Care Nurse. 2007 Aug;27(4):32-6, 38-9; quiz 40. PMID:17671243.
5. Charle MVP, Joshy M Easow, Joseph NM, Ravishankar M, Kumar S, Umadevi S. Incidence and risk factors of ventilator associated pneumonia in a tertiary care hospital. AMJ 2013;6(4):178-182.
6. Lawrence P, Fulbrook P. The ventilator care bundle and its impact on ventilator-associated pneumonia: a review of the evidence. Nurs. Critical Care. 2011 Sep-Oct;16(5):222-34. doi: 10.1111/j.1478-5153.2010.00430.x. PMID: 21824227.

7. <https://www.hpsc.ie/carebundles>.
8. (ATS/DSA Guidelines2005).
9. www.Wikipedia.
10. A Prospective Study,Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute, Pondicherry , M.V. Pravin Charles, et. al,2013
11. Yogesh Harde.(2013).“Detection of ventilator associated pneumonia, using clinical pulmonaryinfectionscore(CPIS)incriticallyillneurologicalpatients.”Journalof Anesthesiology&Science,3(1):225–231.
12. VishalBShete,et.AI,2011Vishal,B,Shete.(2012).“Using evidence– based practice to prevent ventilator associatedPneumonia”.JournalOfCriticalCareNurse,32:21-31.
13. A collaborative multi- centre cohort study, Rello J, et. at, 2013, A study on “Effectiveness of ventilator bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on mechanical ventilation,salem”, by MS. Ligi Rachel Daniel.
14. A Prospective longitudinal study, adult intensive care unit, Hera general hospitals, Makah, Kingdom of Saudi Arebia, Bukhari. S. Z, et.at, 2012.A study on “Effectiveness of ventilator bundle on prevention of ventilator associated pneumonia among patients on mechanical ventilation,salem”, by MS. Ligi Rachel Daniel.